

Exploration of 4(1H)-pyridones as a novel family of potent antimalarial inhibitors of the plasmodial cytochrome bc1

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A novel family of antimalarials based on the 4(1H)-pyridone scaffold is described. The compounds display potent antimalarial activity against *Plasmodium falciparum* *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Like atovaquone, 4(1H)-pyridones exert their antimalarial action by inhibiting selectively the electron-transport chain in *P. falciparum* at the cytochrome bc1 level (complex III). However, despite the similar mechanism of action, no cross-resistance with atovaquone has been found, suggesting that the binding mode of 4(1H)-pyridones might be different from that of atovaquone. The medicinal chemistry program, focused on improving potency and physicochemical properties, ultimately led to the discovery of GSK932121, which was progressed efficiently into first time in human studies. However, progression of GSK932121 was terminated when new toxicology results were obtained in the rat with a soluble phosphate prodrug of the candidate, indicating a potentially narrow therapeutic index.

The plasmodial cytochrome b1 as antimalarial target

The spread of chloroquine- and multidrug-resistant *Plasmodium falciparum* strains [1], the limited drug armamentarium currently available against malaria [2], and the signs of emerging resistance to artemisinins [3], the basic component of the current gold standard

artemisinin-combinations therapies for the treatment of malaria, has led to renewed efforts to find novel drugs for the treatment of uncomplicated malaria [4,5]. In this regard, the mitochondrial electron-transport chain of *P. falciparum* is an attractive target for chemotherapy because its functional significance is somewhat different from that of the analogous mammalian system. For example, as malaria parasites satisfy their energy needs mostly by glycolysis, their mitochondrial electron-transport chain does not seem to be essential for ATP production via oxidative phosphorylation, in contrast to aerobic eukaryotic cells. Rather, it is likely to be essential for the parasite as it acts as a sink for the electrons produced in other critical processes such as de novo pyrimidine biosynthesis [6–9]. The sequence of the Plasmodium genome has revealed that the genes encoding enzymes involved in the pyrimidine biosynthetic pathway have been evolutionarily conserved whereas those involved in pyrimidine salvage have not [10], therefore, malaria parasites rely completely on full mitochondrial function to maintain an intracellular pyrimidine pool necessary for the synthesis of nucleic acids, glycoproteins and phospholipids.

The clinical utility of this target has been demonstrated with the success of atovaquone (Figure 1), an antimalarial drug that was introduced into therapy in 1997 in a combination with proguanil as GlaxoSmithKline Malarone®. Atovaquone inhibits mitochondrial electron transport by binding to the Q_o site of cytochrome bc₁ complex, where the oxidation of ubiquinol takes place [11].

Figure 1. Atovaquone

When used as a single agent, resistance to atovaquone developed rapidly in *falciparum* malaria as a result of mutations within a catalytic domain of the cytochrome bc₁ [12], preventing its use as monotherapy. Used in combination with atovaquone, proguanil (prodrug of the DHFR inhibitor cycloguanil) acts as a mitochondrial sensitizer that synergizes with atovaquone. Despite its high cost and the reported malarone treatment failures due to resistance [13], the combination atovaquone/proguanil is currently used for treatment of multidrug-resistant malaria and also for prophylaxis in areas with chloroquine resistance [14].

Research into novel inhibitors of the para-site mitochondrial function is currently an active area of interest in the antimalarial field. Novel potent inhibitors of the plasmodial cytochrome bc₁ such as decoquinate [15] and other quinolones [16–19] and benzothiazepines [20] have been recently reported in the literature, demonstrating the potential of mitochondrial inhibition in the development of novel potent multistage therapeutic agents with efficacy not only against blood stages, but also against liver, mosquito and presexual forms of the parasite (gametocytes) [21].

From clopidol to antimalarial 5-(4-phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridones

In an effort to find novel and affordable anti-malarials and to develop compounds that overcome some of the issues found with atovaquone, scientists at the former Wellcome Laboratories and more recently at GlaxoSmithKline's Diseases of the Developing World Centre at Tres Cantos (Madrid, Spain) have developed a Medicinal Chemistry program based on 4(1H)-pyridones related to the anticoccidial drug clopidol (Figure 2). Clopidol was long known for its weak antimalarial activity in animal models [22], being active at 160 mg/kg in a *Plasmodium berghei* murine model, curative in a *Plasmodium gallinaceum* model in chicks at the same dose and was tested against human malaria in the 1960s. There is strong evidence that the anticoccidial action of clopidol is related to the inhibition of mitochondrial electron transport chain [23,24].

The original medicinal chemistry strategy, based on the hypothesis that the 4(1H)-pyridone core was acting as an ubiquinone mimetic, focused initially on position C5 by replacing one of the chlorine atoms present at clopidol with different lipophilic moieties (Figure 2) [25]. As shown in Table 1, the introduction of a flexible saturated N-octyl chain, resembling the known antimalarial endochin [26,27] or a 4-chlorophenyl group resulted in 1 and 2, respectively, with modest in vitro antimalarial activity [28] in the *P. falciparum* strain T9–69 [29]. It is noteworthy that the introduction of more lipophilic side chains bearing aromatic rings such as 4'-chlorodiphenyl and particularly 4-(4-chlorophenoxy)phenyl and 4-(4-chlorophenylmethoxy)phenyl produced a significant increase in the in vitro activity (3–5). Introduction of more lipophilic groups such as trifluoromethyl instead of a chlorine atom and a C-C triple bond as a rigid linker between the phenyl rings produced 6 and 7, respectively, with antimalarial activity in vitro in the low nano-molar range against the *P. falciparum* sensitive 3D7A strain. Particularly noteworthy was the loss of antimalarial activity observed when the flexibility around the pyridone ring was increased by introducing a methylene group as a linker between the 4(1H)-pyridone ring and the first aromatic ring in the lipophilic side

chain (8 & 9), in comparison with their more rigid chlorinated analogs (4 & 5), where the phenyl ring is conjugated to the pyridone core.

Figure 2. Antimalarial 4(1H)-pyridones

Table 1. Antimalarial activity of 4(1H)-pyridones: influence of the lipophilic side chain.

Compound	Lipophilic chain	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> T9-96 IC ₅₀ (μM) [†]	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> 3D7A IC ₅₀ (μM) [†]
1	n-C ₈ H ₁₇	4	ND
2		2.5	ND
3		0.15	ND
4		0.05	ND
5		ND	0.1
6		0.06	0.006
7		ND	0.003
8		ND	0.7
9		ND	>1
Clodidol	Cl	20	ND
Atovaquone	–	0.003	0.0002
Chloroquine	–	0.07	0.03

[†]¹³H-Hypoxanthine uptake assay. Modification of the semi-automated microdilution Desjardins technique [28]. ND: Not defined.

Table 2. Antimalarial activity of 5-(phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridones.

P. falc. IC₅₀ (μM)[†]

Compound	R1	R2	X	Isomer	R3	T9-96	3D7A
10	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	p	4-CF ₃	0.5	ND
11	CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	p	4-CF ₃	0.06	0.012
12	CH ₃	CH ₃	Br	P	4-CF ₃	0.03	0.02
13	CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	p	3-CF ₃	0.03	0.005
14	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	p	4-OCF ₃	0.16	ND
15	CH ₃	CH ₃	Cl	p	4-OCF ₃	0.03	0.005
16	CH ₃	CH ₃	Br	p	4-OCF ₃	0.03	0.006
17	CH ₃	CH ₃	CF ₃	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.025
18	CH ₃	CH ₃	CF ₃	p	3-CF ₃	ND	0.04
19	CH ₃	CH ₃	NO ₂	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.03
20	CH ₃	CH ₃	OCH ₃	p	3-CF ₃	ND	0.3
21	CH ₃	CH ₃	OH	p	3-CF ₃	ND	1
22	CH ₃	CH ₃		p	4-OCF ₃	ND	1.3
23	CH ₃	CH ₃	Ph	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.7
24	CH ₃	CH ₃	Br	m	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.007
25	CH ₃	CH ₃	Br	o	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.4
26	H	CH ₃	Br	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.2
27	CH ₃	H	Br	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	0.1
28	CH ₃	CF ₃	Br	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	>1
29	H	CF ₃	Br	p	4-OCF ₃	ND	>1

[†]³H-hypoxanthine uptake assay. Modification of the semi-automated microdilution technique of Desjardins [28]. m: Meta; ND: Not defined; o: Ortho; p: Para.

The introduction of trifluoromethyl or trifluoromethoxy groups to replace the chlorine substituent in the lipophilic tail (Table 2), was well tolerated and maintained robust in vitro antimalarial activity. Concerning substitutions at the pyridone ring, in general, the presence of halogen atoms at position C3 (X = Cl, Br) increased significantly the in vitro antimalarial activity relative to their analogs bearing hydrogen (typically tenfold improvement of IC₅₀), with little or no difference between 3-chloro and 3-bromo derivatives (10–12). Other electron-withdrawing groups such as CF₃ or NO₂ were tolerated (17–19), but provided no improvement in antimalarial activity while electron-donating substituents (X = OH, OMe, aminoalkyl) or phenyl resulted in a clear drop of activity (20–23). Concerning the effect of the relative position of the phenoxy side chain, the potent activity displayed by the compound substituted at para position is retained in the meta isomer, but drops in the ortho analogue (16, 24 and 25, respectively). Removal of either 2- or 6- methyl groups resulted in a significant drop in the in vitro activity, which is exacerbated by the electron-withdrawing CF₃ (26–29).

The 5-(phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridones shown in Tables 1 & 2 are more potent than chloroquine in vitro when tested against erythrocytic stages of the parasite, showing >500-fold improvement in potency over clodolol for inhibition of *P. falciparum* growth in vitro. In addition, pyridones also have shown in vitro and in vivo activity against liver stages (not reported here), indicating potential for use in antimalarial prophylaxis [30]. The optimization of the 5-phenoxy-phenyl series delivered lead compounds 13, 15 and 16. As shown in Table 3, chlorinated derivatives 13 and 15 displayed many desirable properties for an antimalarial drug: high efficacy in vitro and in vivo in the *P. yoelii* murine model and activity against resistant strains to marketed antimalarials including the atovaquone/chloroquine-resistant clone FCR3-A. In addition, 13 and 15 inhibited selectively the plasmodial ubiquinol:cytochrome c oxidoreductase (Cytbc1) with potencies in the low nanomolar range, similar to the whole cell in vitro activities seen against *P. falciparum* cultures (Table 3). The IC₅₀ for human Cytbc1 was approximately 150–250-fold higher than the IC₅₀ for Plasmodium Cytbc1, while the whole-cell selectivity index is >500–1000-fold (measured as cytotoxic IC₅₀ in HepG2 cells vs IC₅₀ for the Pf 3D7 *P. falciparum* strain). It is noteworthy that the cytotoxicity assays were hampered by the low solubility of the samples in the media used for IC₅₀ determination in the HepG2 cell line (the data show the maximum concentration reached in the media without precipitation of the sample).

The potent activity observed against atovaquone-resistant strain FCR3A suggests that, despite the similar mechanism of action, the binding modes of the antimalarial 4(1H)-pyridones and atovaquone to the active site of the plasmodial cytochrome bc1 might be different.

On the basis of their good in vivo efficacy in the *Plasmodium yoelii* murine model, compounds 13 and 15 were tested in Aotus monkeys infected with *P. falciparum*, the primate model closest to human malaria. Both 13 and 15 were completely curative after oral administration of seven daily doses of 10 mg/kg [31]. The oral bio-availability in mice was excellent from solution formulations at low dose [32,33] ($F = 50\text{--}100\%$ at <1 mg/kg), but dropped dramatically when administered in suspension at higher doses ($F \approx 20\%$ at 10 mg/kg), presumably due to solubility or dissolution rate limited oral absorption from the solid dosage form, as expected for classical BCS Class II compounds (low aqueous solubility and high permeability) [34].

Table 3. Profile of 5-(4-phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridones 13 and 15.

Biological profile

Compound	<i>In vitro</i> IC ₅₀ (μM)					<i>In vivo</i> (mg/kg)	
	Target Cytbc1		Whole cell			4 day <i>Plasmodium yoelii</i> CD1 mice	
	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	Human (HEK293)	<i>P. falc.</i> [†] 3D7A	<i>P. falc.</i> [†] FCR3A	Human HepG2	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀
13	0.002	0.5	0.005	0.001	>2.5	0.13	0.16
15	0.002	0.3	0.005	0.002	>5	0.2	0.4

Physicochemical properties and absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion profile

Compound	Solubility (μg/ml)				CHIlogD [‡]			Papp MDCK (nm/s)	Protein binding (%)
	pH 2–12	FeSSI	F	FaSSIF pH = 2	pH = 7.4	pH = 10.5			
13	<0.1	4.8	0.9	2.61	2.67	2.64	434	99	
15	<0.1	3	0.9	2.75	2.79	2.77	357	>99.8	

Pharmacokinetics profile

Compound	CD1 mouse					Beagle dog				
	V _{ss} (l/kg) [§]	Cl (ml/min/kg) [§]	t _{1/2} (h) [§]	C _{max} (mg/ml) [¶]	%F [¶]	V _{ss} (l/kg) [#]	Cl (ml/min/kg) [#]	t _{1/2} (h) [#]	C _{max} (mg/ml) [¶]	%F [¶]
13	0.9	3	3.6	0.81	23	2.6	0.6	61	0.02	3
15	1.2	0.6	24.1	0.9	20	2.9	0.2	143	0.03	4

[†]³H-Hypoxanthine uptake assay. Modification of the semi-automated microdilution technique of Desjardins [28].

[‡]Chromatographic hydrophobicity index [35].

[§]Solution in 1% DMSO/7.5% PEG/20% encapsin/saline pH = 6; intravenous (0.2 mg/kg).

[#]Oral gavage: suspension 1% methyl cellulose; per orem (10 mg/kg).

[¶]Solution in 1% DMSO/7.5% PEG/20% encapsin/saline; intravenous (0.05 mg/kg).

[¶]Oral gavage: suspension 1% methyl cellulose; per orem (2 mg/kg).

Compound 15 was progressed to preclinical studies on the basis of its remarkable antimalarial profile and long half-life, which was ideal for a single-dose treatment. Its high lipophilicity [35] and protein binding (Table 3), poor solubility in aqueous media in a wide range of pH values ($S < 0.1 \mu\text{g/ml}$, $\text{pH} = 2\text{--}12$) as well as in biorelevant simulated fluids (FeSSIF, FaSSIF) [36] and the low oral bioavailability in preclinical species were identified as the main issues for the development of this compound.

In preclinical safety studies, 15 displayed nonlinear pharmacokinetics, resulting in an inability to raise systemic exposures above a certain limit. No visible signs of toxicity in the repeat dose studies in both rat and dog were observed at the highest exposures. However, although no clinical findings were observed in the 14-day dog study, the progression of 15 was discontinued because of mild and reversible histopathological findings seen in skeletal and cardiac muscles. These alterations were tentatively attributed to the accumulation of the drug into these tissues, probably as a result of its high lipophilicity and long half-life in the dog ($t_{1/2} = 143 \text{ h}$).

Back-up 5-(4-phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridones with improved physicochemical properties

Given the results obtained with the first preclinical candidate, the back-up program was focused on designing novel less lipophilic 5-(4-phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridone derivatives, with improved solubility and oral bioavailability, as well as a shorter half-life in order to prevent possible toxic effects due to accumulation. As the antimalarial activity was particularly sensitive to the introduction of polar groups at the lipophilic side chain, the medicinal chemistry strategy was driven by chemical transformations at the hydrophilic 4(1H)-pyridone core. As mentioned previously (Table 2), introduction of ionizable tertiary amines (22), methoxy or polar hydroxyl groups (20 and 21, respectively) at position C3 of the pyridone ring resulted in a significant or complete loss of antimalarial activity [25]. Therefore, the new medicinal chemistry back-up program was focused on reducing lipophilicity by attaching polar hydrophilic groups such as CH_2OH or ionizable moieties such as tertiary amines and carboxyl groups at the yet unexplored C2 and C6 positions of the 4(1H)-pyridone ring. As shown in Table 4, the introduction of ionizable tertiary amines, carboxylic acid or amide at positions C2 or C6 produced similar results to those observed for position C3, leading to inactive compounds ($\text{IC}_{50} > 0.25 \mu\text{M}$) irrespective of their relative position in the 4(1H)-pyridone ring (32–34 & 37–41) [37].

Table 4. *In vitro* activity of 5-(4-phenoxyphenyl)-4(1*H*)-pyridones with polar/ionizable groups at C2/C6.

Compound	Y	Z	R	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> IC ₅₀ 3D7A (μM) [†]
13	CH ₃	CH ₃	3-CF ₃	0.005
15	CH ₃	CH ₃	4-OCF ₃	0.005
30	CH ₂ OH	CH ₃	4-OCF ₃	0.13
31	CH ₂ OH	CH ₃	3-CF ₃	0.12
32	CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	CH ₃	4-OCF ₃	>0.25
33		CH ₃	4-OCF ₃	>0.25
34		CH ₃	4-OCF ₃	>0.25
35	CH ₃	CH ₂ OH	4-OCF ₃	0.002
36	CH ₃	CH ₂ OH	3-CF ₃	0.003
37	CH ₃	CH ₂ N(CH ₃) ₂	4-OCF ₃	>0.25
38	CH ₃		4-OCF ₃	>0.25
39	CH ₃		4-OCF ₃	>0.25
40	CH ₃	CO ₂ H	4-OCF ₃	>0.25
41	CH ₃	CO ₂ N(Me) ₂	4-OCF ₃	>0.25

[†]³H-hypoxanthine uptake assay. Modification of the semi-automated microdilution technique of Desiardins [23].

However, the polar hydroxymethyl group CH₂OH showed a very different behaviour. Thus, while the CH₂OH group induced a significant reduction in the *in vitro* antimalarial activity when located at position C2 in compounds **30** and **31**, their isomers **35** and **36**, with the CH₂OH group attached at position C6 retained the high level of antimalarial activity observed for the parent nonhydroxylated counterparts **15** and **13**, respectively. As shown in **Table 5**, **35** displays better physicochemical properties than its precursor **15**. The lipophilicity of **35** expressed in terms of CHlogD [35] is slightly lower in comparison to other pyridones while retaining similar levels of antimalarial activity *in vitro* and *in vivo*. In addition, **35** is significantly more soluble in FeS-SIF and less protein bound than **15**, with high permeability in MDCK cell line. In common with **15**, hydroxymethyl derivative **35** inhibits the plasmodial Cytbc1 in the low nanomolar range, similar to the whole cell *in vitro* activities seen against *P. falciparum* cultures. However, the ratio of mammalian to parasite IC₅₀ for Cytbc1 in both

human HEK293 and rat H9C2 cells (57- and 86-fold, respectively) is slightly lower than for 15 (150-fold).

Special mention should be made of the cytotoxicity measured in the rat myocardium H9C2 cell line that was adapted to grow in the presence of galactose instead of glucose as a carbon source in the media. Under these conditions, the H9C2 cells rely on mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation (respiration) rather than fermentative glycolysis, thus circumventing the predominant generation of ATP via fermentation observed in highly proliferative cells (Crab-tree effect) and increasing the susceptibility of the cells to mitochondrial toxicants [38]. Mitochondrial impairment was assessed by an ATP-depletion assay. As shown in Table 5 the in vitro ratio of mammalian vs *P. falciparum* 3D7 whole-cell IC₅₀ was 2300 and 1600 for rat H9C2 and for the parent non hydroxylated counterparts 15 and 13, respectively.

As shown in Table 5, 35 displays better physicochemical properties than its precursor 15. The lipophilicity of 35 expressed in terms of CHlogD [35] is slightly lower in comparison to other pyridones while retaining similar levels of antimalarial activity in vitro and in vivo. In addition, 35 is significantly more soluble in FeSSIF and less protein bound than 15, with high permeability in MDCK cell line.

Table 5. Profile of 5-(4-phenoxyphenyl)-4(1H)-pyridones 15 & 35.

<i>Biological profile</i>											
Compound	<i>In vitro</i> IC ₅₀ (μM)				Whole cell				<i>In vivo</i> (mg/kg)		
	Target Cytbc1		Rat H9C2		Plasmodium falciparum [†]		Cytotoxicity		4-day Plasmodium yoelii CD1 mice		4-day Plasmodium falciparum SCID mice
	Plasmodium falciparum	Human HEK293		D7A	FCR3A	Rat H9C2 (ATP depl.)	Human HepG2	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀	ED ₅₀	ED ₉₀
35	0.007	0.4	0.6	0.006	0.006	14	10	0.3	0.6	0.5	0.6
15	0.002	0.3	NT	0.005	0.002	NT	>5	0.2	0.4	ND	ND
<i>Physicochemical properties and absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion profile</i>											
Compound	Solubility (μg/ml)			CHIlogD [‡]			PappMDCK (nm/s)	Protein binding (%)			
	pH 2-12	FeSSIF	FaSSIF	pH = 2	pH = 7.4	pH = 10.5					
35	<0.1	200	0.7	2.43	2.42	2.2	712	97			
15	<0.1	3	0.9	2.75	2.79	2.77	357	>99.8			
<i>Pharmacokinetics profile</i>											
Compound	CD1 mouse					Beagle dog					
	V _{ss} (l/kg) [§]	Cl (ml/min/kg) [§]	t _{1/2} (h) [§]	C _{max} (mg/ml) [¶]	t _{1/2} (h) [¶]	V _{ss} (l/kg) [#]	Cl (ml/min/kg) [#]	t _{1/2} (h) [#]	C _{max} (mg/ml) ^{††}	%F _t [†]	
35	1	3	3.8	1.1	5	2.8	0.8	42	0.3	16	
15	1.2	0.6	24.1	0.9	2	2.9	0.2	143	0.03	4	

[†]H-Hypoxanthine uptake assay. Modification of the semi-automated microdilution technique of Desjardins [28].
[‡]Chromatographic hydrophobicity index [35].
[§]Solution in 1% DMSO/7.5% PEG/20% encapsin/saline pH = 6; intravenous (0.2 mg/kg).
[¶]Oral gavage: suspension 1% methyl cellulose; per orem (10 mg/kg).
[#]Solution in 1% DMSO/7.5% PEG/20% encapsin/saline; intravenous (0.05 mg/kg).
^{††}Oral gavage: suspension 1% methyl cellulose; per orem (2 mg/kg).

In common with 15, hydroxymethyl derivative 35 inhibits the plasmodial Cytbc1 in the low nanomolar range, similar to the whole cell in vitro activities seen against *P. falciparum* cultures. However, the ratio of mammalian to parasite IC₅₀ for Cytbc1 in both human HEK293 and rat H9C2 cells (57- and 86-fold, respectively) is slightly lower than for 15 (150-fold).

Special mention should be made of the cytotoxicity measured in the rat myocardium H9C human HepG2 cell lines, respectively. Thus, similar to what we have observed with other

pyridones, the whole cell mammalian to parasite selectivity ratio was significantly higher than the one measured in the corresponding biochemical assays with isolated mitochondria.

As expected, the higher solubility of 35 in comparison with its non-hydroxylated analogue 15, particularly in FeSSIF, translated into a significant enhancement in the oral bioavailability from the solid dosage form (suspension in 1% methylcellulose) both in mice (50% vs 20%) and particularly in dogs (16% vs 4%). Furthermore, 35 seemed to be more sensitive to metabolic degradation evidenced by the significant increase in clearance and reduction in half-life in both mice and dog, possibly by direct elimination via Phase II metabolism as suggested by the presence of the corresponding glucuronic acid conjugate in a metabolite determination study (data not shown here). Concerning in vivo efficacy, it is noteworthy that in spite of its shorter half-life, compound 35 has displayed an outstanding in vivo efficacy (ED₉₀ = 0.6 mg/kg) in both *P. yoelii* and *P. falciparum* murine malaria models [39].

In spite of its better solubility and improved PK profile, 35 also demonstrated nonlinear pharmacokinetics in preclinical species with decreased oral bioavailability at high doses of the solid dosage form. However, it is important to point out that significantly higher systemic exposures of 35 were reached in a repeat dose study in dog in comparison with compound 15 without similar toxic effects in the skeletal and cardiac muscles.

As no dose-limiting toxicity was observed in preclinical species, 35 (as GSK932121) was progressed to a first time in human study (FTIH). In order to optimize oral bioavailability, the formulation used in the FTIH study consisted of nanomilled 35 particles [40] coated with a mixture of sodium lauryl sulfate, mannitol and hyprom focus of the back-up program shifted towards finding water-soluble prodrugs of **35**. When tested in animals, this formulation provided promising results, delivering higher oral bioavailability than other formulations. However, it should be noted that complex formulations may significantly increase the cost of goods of the final active pharmaceutical ingredient – an important consideration in the development of antimalarials as low cost of goods is a requirement for any drug intended for the treatment of malaria in developing countries [101].

In parallel, as the introduction of polar moieties and the use of special formulations had limited success in increasing the oral bioavailability of the compounds in preclinical species, the focus of the back-up program shifted towards finding water-soluble prodrugs of **35**.

The prodrug approach

From a practical point of view, although the preparation of prodrugs usually involves additional chemical steps from the final parent drug, the elimination of solubilizing excipients for oral dosing and the likely increase of oral bioavailability can lead to important

dose and cost reductions and provide a more convenient dosing regimen, especially for high-dose compounds [41,42].

From a synthetic point of view, **35** has two hydroxyl groups where a suitable promoiety could be attached: the C4-OH group present at the hydroxypyridine tautomeric form and the new primary hydroxyl group C6-CH₂OH (Figure 3). All the efforts devoted to the preparation of prodrugs by introduction of either basic carbamates [43] or esters [41] at the C4-OH proved to be unsuccessful, leading to materials that were either chemically unstable or semisolids difficult to develop.

Figure 3. Prodrug strategy. Water-soluble phosphate ester of **35**

In this regard, the presence of a primary hydroxyl group in **35** offered new opportunities for the preparation of soluble and chemically stable prodrugs. One of the most commonly used prodrug strategies to increase aqueous solubility of compounds bearing hydroxyl groups such as **35** is the development of water-soluble phosphate esters [44]. Phosphate esters increase solubility, often several orders of magnitude, by virtue of the dianionic phosphate group [45], and upon oral administration, undergo rapid bioconversion at the intestinal brush border by action of membrane-bound alkaline phosphatases [41,46], releasing high concentrations of the parent drug in the vicinity of the mucosal membrane. To achieve maximal absorption, it is ideally required that the poorly soluble parent drug possesses high permeability across membranes as is the case with **35**.

Phosphate ester prodrug **42** (Figure 3) was easily accessible from **35** and chemically very stable in different aqueous solutions in a wide range of pH and temperatures, remaining unaltered after 48h in all media tested. However, in the presence of alkaline phosphatase, it decomposed quickly and released the parent drug ($t_{1/2} < 5$ min). As expected, the presence

of a bis-ionized phosphate moiety at physiological pH yielded a dramatic GI-relevant pH-solubility increase compared with the parent compound ($S > 100$ mg/ml at pH = 5).

In order to assess the effect of increased solubility on pharmacokinetics, both **35** and its prodrug **42** were administered orally to rats. Figure 4 shows the oral exposures to parent drug 35 after administration of the **35** in suspension in comparison with the exposures observed after administration of its prodrug **42** in aqueous solution. Although the exposure increase was not perfectly linear over the range of doses administered, the blood levels of parent 35 were significantly higher after administration of its soluble phosphate prodrug **42**. As an example, the systemic exposures to **35** in terms of both AUC_{0–24} and C_{max} after administration of its prodrug 42 at 387 mg/kg as di-sodium salt in buffered aqueous solution (300 mg/kg equivalent dose of 35), were approximately tenfold higher than the maximum exposures reached after administration of 35 in suspension at 1000 mg/kg.

Figure 4. Prodrug effect: blood levels of 35 (GSK932121) measured in rats after oral administration of its prodrug 42 in buffered aqueous solution at 30, 100 and 300 mg/Kg. Blood levels of 35 administered orally at 30 and 1000 mg/Kg in suspension (20PEG/20%captisol) are also included for comparison.

FTIH study

The purpose of the FTIH study was to evaluate the safety and tolerability of **35** in comparison with placebo, and to investigate the pharmacokinetics of the compound in man. Eight healthy adult male subjects received single doses of **35** (3 mg; n = 4 and 30 mg; n = 4) along with four subjects who received placebo. The compound was safe and well-tolerated in these subjects: all observed adverse events were mild (except for one case of moderate viral gastroenteritis) and none was considered drug-related by the investigator; no clinically significant abnormal findings in electrocardiograms, vital signs, clinical chemistry or hematology were reported. AUC(0–∞) for **35** was approximately dose-proportional between 3–30 mg in the fasted state, while C_{max} was slightly less than dose proportional. Mean t_{1/2} values ranged from 36.6–40.3 h and the compound was readily absorbed with t_{max} values ranging from 1.0–4.0 h (Table 6; Figures 5 & 6). In parallel with the FTIH study, prodrug **42** was progressed into preclinical studies as a potential back-up for **35** on the basis of its outstanding physicochemical and pharmacokinetic profile. However, unexpected acute toxicity was observed in rats after oral administration of prodrug **42**, which was subsequently replicated by dosing **35** alone through intraperitoneal administration at similar exposure levels to those achieved with its prodrug. As a plausible hypothesis, the toxicity observed in rats was attributed to the inhibition of the mammalian bc1 mitochondrial complex by parent compound **35**. The FTIH study with **35** was placed on hold and later terminated despite its uneventful progress through the first two dose levels. Therefore, it was not known whether compound **35** would continue to exhibit dose-proportional PK at higher doses in humans.

Table 6. First time in human study: summary of selected GSK932121 pharmacokinetic parameters in healthy volunteers.

Dose	N	AUC _(0-t) [†] (ng h/ml)	AUC _(0-∞) [†] (ng h/ml)	C _{max} [†] (ng/ml)	T _{max} [‡] (h)	T _{1/2} [‡] (h)
3 mg	4	632 (46)	740 (50)	25.7 (24)	2.0 (2.0-3.0)	40.3 (56.8)
30 mg	4	7688 (63)	7796 (63)	179 (19)	3.0 (1.0-4.0)	36.6 (35.6)

[†]Geometric mean (CV%).

[‡]Median (range).

Figure 5.

Pharmacokinetic profile of **35** (GSK932121) in healthy volunteers at 3 mg single dose

Figure 6.

Pharmacokinetic profile of **35** (GSK932121) in healthy volunteers at 30 mg single dose

Novel antimalarial 4(1H)-pyridones

Inhibitors of the plasmodial mitochondrial electron-transport chain have received considerable attention in the past few years [6,15–20]. However, although the success of potent Pf Cytbc1 inhibitors such as atovaquone validates the mitochondrial electron-transport chain as an important, yet largely untapped target in the antimalarial field, the key challenges in this field still remain: to find Pf Cytbc1 inhibitors with acceptable ADME properties and high selectivity for the parasite target in comparison to the mammalian counterpart. It is not a coincidence that the inhibition of the plasmodial Cytbc1 has been described in a recent paper as a ‘complex issue’ [47].

In a continuous effort to obtain more selective and bioavailable 4(1H)-pyridones, we have performed chemical transformations focused on reducing lipophilicity and increasing solubility by introducing nitrogen heterocycles such as pyridine and basic tertiary amines at the yet largely underexplored lipophilic side chain (Figure 7). As a result, novel families of potent antimalarial 4(1H)-pyridones with improved properties have been obtained and will be published in the near future.

Figure 7. Novel antimalarial 4(1H)-pyridones

Future perspective

Despite the complexity and difficulties associated with the development of inhibitors of the mitochondrial electron transport chain as antimalarials, 4(1H)-pyridones and other Plasmodium mitochondrial inhibitors that overcome developability issues resulting from their high lipophilicity and poor physicochemical properties as well as other potential hurdles related to insufficient selectivity against the mammalian target, could become an important addition to the antimalarial armamentarium. In addition, as the parasite needs some level of mitochondrial function in most of its stages, such drugs may be efficacious not only against blood forms, but also against other stages of the parasite such as liver and mosquito forms thus providing additional efficacy as preventive and transmission blocking

agents. Therefore, with the broadening scope of antimalarial drug discovery today, parasite mitochondrial inhibition is likely to remain an area of active interest in the future.

Conclusion

Inhibiting the mitochondrial electron-transport chain of the Plasmodium parasite is a challenging but promising approach for antimalarial drug development that has been validated by the successful marketing of atovaquone. Our experience has demonstrated the potential for development of novel compounds that, while sharing a similar mechanism of action with atovaquone, retain potent activity against atovaquone-resistant strains. Furthermore, as the mitochondria are involved in important processes in different stages of the parasite's lifecycle [7,8,9], inhibitors of the electron transport chain may provide efficacy not only for treatment of the disease, but also as multistage agents suitable for prophylaxis and transmission blockade [21].

Our efforts with several antimalarial 4(1H)-pyridones and in particular with clinical candidate GSK932121 have also highlighted some possible issues for compounds with this mechanism of action, among them low oral bioavailability and insufficient target selectivity. As high lipophilicity may be a prerequisite for the antimalarial activity of these compounds, attaining good oral bioavailability may be challenging due to the limited solubility of the compounds. Therefore, an optimal balance between antimalarial potency, physicochemical characteristics and PK properties is essential. While formulation approaches can be helpful in addressing this issue, their impact on the cost of goods needs to be carefully assessed.

The prodrug approach has been a successful strategy in overcoming limited oral bioavailability due to poor solubility and may be considered early in the development process. As inhibition of the mammalian respiratory chain could result in serious toxicity, high selectivity against mammalian mitochondria is of paramount importance in ensuring the safety of the compound. Selectivity should be confirmed *in vitro* both at the level of the target and at the level of the whole cell. To ensure that a wide therapeutic index is present *in vivo*, it is recommended that sufficiently high exposures to the compounds should be studied in preclinical species. If oral dosing provides limited exposures, other options should be explored early in the development process, for example, parenteral administration and prodrugs.

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Financial & competing interest disclosure

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Ethical issues

All animal studies were ethically reviewed and carried out in accordance with European Directive 86/609/EEC and the GSK Policy on the Care, Welfare and Treatment of Animals. The human study was carried out in Melbourne (Australia) after approval by an ethics committee and in accordance with the principles set out Financial & competing interests disclosure The work described here has been carried out in GlaxoSmithKline's Diseases of the Developing World in the Declaration of Helsinki and good clinical practice guidelines. All participating subjects provided written informed consent.

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